

Understanding online violence against women in Bangladesh: Sociocultural drivers, legal awareness, and institutional responses

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Article Info

Article history:

Received March 7, 2026

Revised April 17, 2026

Accepted April 20, 2026

Keywords:

Bangladesh, Cyber harassment, digital safety, legal frameworks, online violence against women, technology-facilitated gender-based violence

ABSTRACT

The rapid advancement of digital technology and widespread internet access in Bangladesh have created new opportunities for communication, education, and engagement, particularly for women. However, these developments have also led to new forms of crime, including digital gender-based violence. This study examines the perceived prevalence, sociocultural dimensions, and legal aspects of online violence against young digitally active women in Bangladesh. Using a quantitative research design supported by qualitative findings, the study found that online violence against women is perceived to be highly prevalent among internet users in Bangladesh. Many participants reported that they experienced multiple forms of abuse, including harassment, impersonation, hate speech, stalking, sextortion, and doxing. The findings further showed that harassment is not limited to anonymous online offenders, as perpetrators were also perceived to include acquaintances, friends, and intimate partners, reflecting offline power dynamics in digital spaces. Participants also reported serious psychological effects, including anxiety and emotional distress. Despite existing legal frameworks, respondents expressed limited confidence in institutional responses. Fear of social stigmatisation, lack of awareness of legal remedies, and mistrust of enforcement mechanisms were identified as major barriers to reporting. The study concludes that online violence against women may be reduced through stronger legal enforcement, improved reporting systems, greater public awareness, and gender-sensitive institutional support, helping to create a safer online environment for women.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Over the last decade, Bangladesh has experienced a rapid increase in internet connectivity and the use of digital technologies. Improved access to smartphones, mobile internet services, and social media platforms has significantly influenced communication, economic activities, and social interactions across the country. According to national reports, the number of internet users has risen sharply in recent years, and digital

technologies have become integral to social, political, and economic life (The Business Standard, 2020). The emergence of digital platforms has created new opportunities for women to access education, economic opportunities, information, and political engagement. However, it has also given rise to new forms of gender-based abuse and harassment in digital spaces (Powell et al., 2020; UN Women, 2023).

Online violence against women (OVAW) has become a global concern, as digital platforms have expanded the scope of violence against women. Scholars define OVAW as technology-facilitated violence against women, including cyber harassment, cyber stalking, hate speech, image-based sexual violence, and other forms of digital intimidation (Citron, 2014; Jane, 2017). Research indicates that women who actively participate online as journalists, activists, politicians, or public figures are particularly vulnerable to organised harassment campaigns and misogynistic abuse (Adams & Tichovolsky, 2019; Mantilla, 2015). Such forms of digital violence not only cause emotional harm to victims but also discourage women from participating in online discussions. In this regard, technology-facilitated harassment contributes to the silencing of women's voices in the digital sphere (Henry & Powell, 2018).

In Bangladesh, the expansion of internet access has been accompanied by a notable rise in cases of online harassment against women. Research findings and institutional reports suggest that technology-facilitated harassment has become a major issue in the country. For example, a national study by ActionAid Bangladesh reported that 63.51% of women internet users had experienced some form of online harassment, representing a sharp increase from 50.19% in 2021 (ActionAid Bangladesh, 2022). Earlier studies conducted by the Bangladesh Legal Aid and Services Trust (BLAST) also found that nearly 73% of female internet users had been victims of cyber harassment. These findings indicate that online harassment of women is not an isolated issue but an embedded feature of the online environment in Bangladesh.

The issue of online harassment is closely linked to the socio-cultural context. Studies suggest that such harassment often reflects patriarchal values. Women who express opinions online or engage in political activities are frequently targeted in attempts to limit their digital presence. Such abuse includes defamatory statements, impersonation, threats, and the circulation of manipulated images intended to damage women's reputations (Akter & Hossain, 2022).

Despite growing awareness of violence against women in digital spaces, many cases remain unreported because of shame, fear of reputational damage, and lack of confidence in case handling. Studies have shown that victims of digital harassment are often reluctant to report incidents because discussing gender-based violence online can lead to victim-blaming (Begum, 2020; Islam & Rahman, 2023). This creates a culture of silence and makes it difficult to assess the true scale of the problem.

In response to rising cybercrime, Bangladesh has introduced several laws to regulate cyber activities and address related offenses, including the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Act 2006, the Digital Security Act 2018, and the Cyber Security Act 2023. However, scholars argue that there remains a significant disconnect between legal provisions, the socio-cultural context, and the practical handling of cases involving violence against women online, making such cases difficult to address effectively (Barker & Jurasz, 2020).

Against this background, the present study examines online violence against women in Bangladesh by exploring the relationship between socio-cultural factors, legal measures, and the occurrence of cyber harassment. Specifically, the study aims to: (1) explore the role of socio-cultural factors in the occurrence of online violence against women; (2) assess the adequacy of legal measures in addressing cyber violence against women; and (3) examine the occurrence of online harassment against women in the digital sphere.

This study seeks to contribute to the emerging literature on technology-based gender violence and to generate evidence that may support the development of more effective policies to address online violence against women in Bangladesh.

It also contributes to the growing body of knowledge on technology-facilitated gender-based violence in several ways. First, it provides updated empirical evidence on the extent and nature of online violence against women in Bangladesh, which remains a relatively under-researched area. Second, it builds on existing scholarship by examining how socio-cultural norms and legal frameworks interact in facilitating online violence against women, as well as how victims respond. Existing studies have often examined legal frameworks or victims' responses separately rather than in an integrated manner. Finally, the study offers policy-relevant insights into how online violence against women in Bangladesh may be addressed more effectively through consideration of both social norms and legal frameworks.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Online violence against women in the digital era

The emergence of digital communication has significantly transformed social interaction, political engagement, and public discourse. Digital platforms have created new opportunities for communication and participation, while also expanding women's access to education, employment, political expression, and activism (Banet-Weiser, 2018; Marwick & Caplan, 2018). However, these same technologies have also enabled new forms of gender-based violence in online spaces.

Scholars commonly describe these forms of abuse as online violence against women (OVAW) or technology-facilitated gender-based violence. OVAW includes cyber harassment, cyberstalking, doxing, impersonation, threats of sexual violence, and the non-consensual distribution of intimate images (Henry & Powell, 2018; Powell & Henry, 2017). Unlike many traditional forms of harassment, online violence can occur across multiple platforms at the same time, reach wider audiences, and continue even after the initial incident. As a result, it can intensify reputational harm, emotional distress, and fear among victims (Sobieraj, 2020).

Early discussions of online harassment often focused on hostile exchanges in internet forums. Jane (2014) explains that such behaviour was commonly described as "flaming", referring to aggressive or abusive interactions between users in online discussion spaces. More recent scholarship, however, understands online harassment as a broader structural problem rather than simply an individual conflict between users. Citron (2014) argues that cyber harassment should be viewed as a civil rights issue because it disproportionately targets marginalised groups, particularly women, and restricts their participation in public discourse. Empirical studies also show that victims of online abuse often experience emotional distress and may withdraw from online discussions to avoid further harassment (Adams & Tichovolsky, 2019; Duggan, 2017). In this way, online violence against women could be understood not only as a personal experience of harm but also as a wider obstacle to women's equal participation in digital public life.

2.2. Gendered dimensions of online harassment

Existing literature suggests that cyber harassment often has a gendered dimension, with women who participate visibly in public life through activism, politics, journalism, and public debate potentially facing greater exposure to organised forms of online abuse. Citron (2014) argues that perpetrators may use threats, defamation, and privacy violations to intimidate victims and discourage them from participating in public discourse.

Jane (2017) uses the term "e-bile" to describe misogynistic online abuse, including sexually offensive and threatening language directed at women. Similarly, Mantilla (2015) uses the concept of "gendertrolling" to explain organised harassment campaigns against women who challenge traditional gender norms. These forms of harassment are often not random or isolated. Rather, they may reflect wider social tensions over women's visibility, voice, and participation in digital spaces. The literature also shows that online platforms can have contradictory effects. On the one hand, they provide important spaces for feminist expression, mobilisation, and public debate. On the other hand, these same spaces may also be used to produce misogynistic backlash against women who speak publicly on social or political issues (Banet-Weiser & Miltner, 2016). Marwick and Caplan (2018) further argue that online harassment can become collective in nature, particularly when groups of users target individuals because of their views or identities.

The above explored research indicates that women, especially those engaged in feminist, political, journalistic, or activist work, may face heightened risks of online harassment. Such harassment can contribute to intimidation, self-censorship, and reduced participation in digital public life.

2.3. Technology-facilitated sexual violence

A growing body of literature examines technology-facilitated sexual violence (TFSV), which generally refers to forms of sexual abuse enabled or amplified through digital technologies. This may include the non-consensual sharing of intimate images, sexual coercion, online sexual blackmail, image-based abuse, and digitally mediated threats of a sexual nature (Henry & Powell, 2015).

In fact, Henry and Powell (2015) argue that digital technologies can extend the scope and impact of sexual violence by making harmful content easier to distribute rapidly, widely, and sometimes anonymously. Image-based sexual abuse may have particularly serious consequences because digital materials can be copied, recirculated, and remain accessible for long periods (Powell & Henry, 2017).

Scholars have also highlighted challenges in responding to these forms of abuse through legal frameworks. McGlynn et al. (2017) argue that some legal approaches have focused primarily on privacy violations, while giving less attention to the gendered and sexualised harms involved. Similarly, Salter and Crofts (2015) note that regulating non-consensual intimate image sharing can be difficult because of jurisdictional issues and the cross-border nature of digital platforms.

2.4. Sociocultural drivers of online violence

Many scholars argue that technology alone does not explain online violence against women, as such abuse is often shaped by wider social and cultural conditions. In this view, online violence may reflect existing gender inequalities, social stereotypes, and power imbalances that are reproduced in digital spaces (Jewkes et al., 2015; Gibbs et al., 2020). Social expectations linked to honour, modesty, and family reputation may also make it more difficult for some women to report abuse, particularly where disclosure carries a risk of blame or social judgement.

These dynamics may be more visible in contexts where traditional gender norms strongly influence women's participation in public life and expression. Research from South Asia suggests that online harassment can sometimes function as a means of discouraging women from taking part in public discussions or expressing views openly in digital spaces (Hossain & McAlpine, 2017).

2.5. Online violence against women in Bangladesh

Although a substantial body of research has examined online violence against women (OVAV) globally, studies focusing specifically on Bangladesh remain relatively limited. Existing reports suggest that cyber harassment has become an important concern for women internet users in the country. For example, ActionAid Bangladesh (2022) reported that more than 63% of surveyed women internet users had experienced some form of online harassment, representing an increase from previous reporting periods.

Other studies and organisational reports have also highlighted the prevalence of cyber harassment among women in Bangladesh. Research by the Bangladesh Legal Aid and Services Trust (BLAST) indicated that approximately 73% of women internet users surveyed had experienced cyber harassment. While findings may vary depending on sampling methods and definitions used, these studies suggest that online abuse is a significant issue requiring continued attention.

Scholars have also drawn attention to the role of sociocultural factors in shaping cyber harassment in Bangladesh. Rahman (2021) suggests that some forms of online abuse may reflect patriarchal attitudes that discourage women's participation in public discussion. Similarly, Akter and Hossain (2022) note that reported incidents of cyber harassment have included defamation, impersonation, and image manipulation intended to damage women's reputations.

Although the issue has received growing recognition, several gaps remain in the existing literature. Much of the current research tends to examine legal frameworks, victims' experiences, or sociocultural influences separately, rather than exploring how these factors interact. In addition, emerging technologies such as deepfakes and artificial intelligence (AI) may create new risks of digital abuse, yet these developments remain underexplored in much of the Bangladesh-focused literature.

2.6. A publicly reported case of digital privacy violation in Bangladesh

An early publicly discussed case of digital abuse against a woman in Bangladesh involved actress and model Sadia Jahan Prova in 2010. The incident concerned the circulation of private photographs and videos online without consent. The case received media attention, including coverage in outlets such as *The Daily Star* and *Dhaka Tribune*, and was discussed as an example of cyber abuse and violation of personal privacy in Bangladesh. Media reporting at the time suggested that the online circulation of these materials was followed by public scrutiny, harassment, and reputational harm, which reportedly affected both the personal and professional life of the actress. Such incidents are often discussed in the literature as forms of image-based sexual abuse, involving the non-consensual distribution of intimate materials in ways that may cause humiliation, distress, or social harm (Henry & Powell, 2018).

The case also illustrates the gendered dimensions of online harassment in Bangladesh. Research on digital misogyny suggests that women in visible public professions, including entertainment, journalism, and activism, may face heightened exposure to reputation-related abuse in digital spaces (Jane, 2017). Once private materials are shared online, they may be repeatedly redistributed across platforms, extending the period of exposure and distress. The Prova case is frequently referenced in discussions of cyber harassment, privacy, and women's digital safety in Bangladesh. More broadly, it highlights the importance of

effective legal safeguards, responsible digital governance, and greater public awareness in addressing technology-facilitated abuse against women.

2.7. Theoretical framework

The present study applies feminist theory as the main theoretical perspective for understanding online violence against women (OVAW) in Bangladesh. Feminist theory generally explains violence against women as linked to wider patterns of gender inequality and unequal power relations within society (Citron, 2014). From this perspective, online harassment is not viewed simply as isolated misconduct by individuals, but as part of broader forms of gender-based violence that may seek to silence, intimidate, or exclude women from public participation, including in digital spaces (Mantilla, 2015).

As digital media have become increasingly important for communication, political engagement, education, and employment, they have also become spaces where existing social inequalities may be reproduced. Feminist scholarship suggests that inequalities present in offline settings can also appear online. For example, women who express political opinions on social media, work as journalists, or participate in activism may face abusive comments, threats, or coordinated trolling campaigns at higher rates than many male counterparts (Jane, 2017). Mantilla (2015) uses the term *gendertrolling* to describe repeated or coordinated forms of gender-based harassment directed at women online.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework for understanding online violence against women in Bangladesh

This perspective also recognises that technology-facilitated abuse may go beyond one-to-one interactions. A single harmful act, such as posting a defamatory comment or sharing manipulated images, can quickly become networked abuse when it is shared, reposted, or amplified by multiple users. In this way, online harassment may involve both individual perpetrators and collective participation, increasing the scale and impact of harm (Banet-Weiser, 2018).

The conceptual framework for this study, grounded in feminist theory, proposes that online violence against women emerges through the interaction of three main factors.

The first is structural gender inequality, including patriarchal norms and gender hierarchies that may shape women's social position and freedom of expression. For example, women who challenge traditional expectations by speaking publicly on social or political issues may be criticised more harshly than men. The second is digital platform features, such as anonymity, virality, and limited accountability. These conditions may make it easier for users to create fake accounts, circulate abusive messages rapidly, or avoid responsibility for harmful conduct. The third is sociocultural dynamics, including stigma, victim blaming, and honour-related social pressures. For example, women subjected to image-based abuse may hesitate to report incidents if they fear reputational harm, family pressure, or negative social judgement.

Within this framework, OVAW may take multiple forms, including harassment, threats, doxing, impersonation, stalking, and image-based abuse. These experiences may also lead to wider consequences, such as anxiety, emotional distress, self-censorship, withdrawal from online discussions, and reduced participation in digital public life.

This framework is particularly relevant in Bangladesh, where social norms relating to honour, modesty, family reputation, and gender expectations may intersect with technological conditions and institutional responses. For instance, a woman facing online harassment may experience not only the abuse itself, but also pressure to remain silent in order to avoid social stigma. Accordingly, the framework provides a useful basis for examining how structural inequality, sociocultural norms, and digital platform characteristics may together shape the occurrence and impact of online violence against women.

3. METHOD

3.1. Research design

This study employed an exploratory sequential mixed-methods design, in which an initial qualitative phase was followed by a quantitative phase (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018; Toyon, 2023). In this design, qualitative data collected through semi-structured interviews were used to generate contextual insights into women's experiences of online violence and to inform the development of the survey instrument.

The qualitative stage enabled an in-depth exploration of participants' lived experiences, perceived forms of abuse, reporting barriers, and views on institutional responses. Insights derived from this phase were subsequently incorporated into the quantitative questionnaire to ensure that the survey reflected contextually relevant issues identified by participants. The second phase involved the administration of a structured survey to examine the distribution of reported experiences, patterns of abuse, levels of legal awareness, and perceptions of available support mechanisms. The integration of qualitative and quantitative evidence allowed the study to combine contextual depth with broader descriptive patterns, thereby providing a more comprehensive understanding of online violence against women in Bangladesh.

3.2. Sampling and participants

Participants in this study were selected from women internet users in Bangladesh who reported having experienced online violence in any form. A purposive sampling strategy was adopted in order to recruit respondents with direct or relevant experience of the phenomenon under investigation. This approach was considered appropriate because the study sought to collect self-reported accounts of online harassment, reporting barriers, and the perceived social, psychological, and institutional impacts of digital abuse.

A total of 100 participants were included in the study. Efforts were made to obtain variation in participants' backgrounds, including age, educational attainment, occupation, and place of residence (urban or rural). Most participants were active users of social media and other digital platforms, making them well placed to provide insight into experiences of online violence in contemporary digital environments.

The final sample was largely composed of younger and relatively highly educated respondents, with many participants being students aged 18–25. Accordingly, the findings should be interpreted primarily as reflecting the experiences and perceptions of young digitally active women rather than the wider population of women in Bangladesh. The study is therefore best understood as an exploratory subgroup analysis rather than a nationally representative survey.

3.3. Data collection

Quantitative data were collected through a structured online questionnaire administered via Google Forms. The questionnaire included items on demographic characteristics, experiences of online harassment, reporting behaviour, awareness of available legal protections, and perceptions of institutional responses.

The online format was selected to facilitate participation, maintain anonymity, and reach digitally active respondents across different locations.

To obtain deeper contextual understanding, semi-structured interviews were also conducted with selected participants. These interviews explored participants' experiences of online violence, perceived psychological and social impacts, coping responses, reporting decisions, and views regarding institutional support mechanisms. The qualitative component provided richer insight into issues that could not be fully captured through closed-ended survey questions (Flick, 2018).

In addition, secondary sources were consulted to support contextual interpretation of the findings. These included academic publications, reports produced by non-governmental organisations, and relevant legal instruments, including the Penal Code (1860), Information and Communication Technology Act (2006), Pornography Control Act (2012), Digital Security Act (2018), and Cyber Security Act (2023). The inclusion of these materials was not intended as a formal legal review or doctrinal analysis. Rather, they were used to provide background context on the regulatory environment surrounding online violence in Bangladesh and to help interpret participants' narratives concerning awareness, reporting experiences, and perceived institutional responses.

Table I. Operationalisation of major variables

Construct	Operational Definition	Survey Item	Response Format
Online harassment	Offensive, insulting, or abusive online comments/messages	Have you experienced insulting or offensive comments online in the last 12 months?	Never / Once / A few times / Frequently
Impersonation	Fake accounts created using respondent's identity	Has anyone created a fake profile using your name or image?	Yes / No
Hate speech	Gender-based abusive or degrading language	Have you received hateful or degrading comments because you are a woman?	Yes / No
Stalking	Repeated unwanted contact or monitoring	Have you experienced repeated unwanted online contact?	Yes / No
Sextortion	Threats involving sexual content	Has anyone threatened or pressured you using intimate content?	Yes / No
Doxing	Sharing personal information without consent	Has anyone shared your personal information online without permission?	Yes / No

In order to enhance clarity in concepts, the major concepts that relate to online violence against women (OVAW) have been operationalised with particular survey questions. Each category of online violence has been defined and measured through questions contained in the survey. Below is a table indicating the operationalisation of major variables in this study.

3.4. Data analysis

Quantitative data obtained from the online questionnaire were analysed using descriptive statistics (Neuman, 2014), including frequencies, percentages, and cross-tabulations, in order to summarise respondents' reported experiences, patterns of online violence, reporting behaviour, and perceptions of institutional responses. Given the exploratory nature of the study and the non-probability sample, the quantitative analysis was primarily descriptive rather than inferential.

Qualitative data derived from the semi-structured interviews were analysed using thematic analysis following the approach outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006). Interview transcripts and notes were reviewed repeatedly to identify recurring themes relating to sociocultural norms, emotional impacts, coping strategies, reporting barriers, and perceptions of institutional support.

Quantitative and qualitative findings were integrated during the interpretation stage. Survey data were used to identify broad patterns in participants' self-reported experiences, while interview narratives were used to provide contextual understanding of those patterns. For example, lower levels of online participation

reported in the survey were interpreted alongside interview accounts describing fear of stigma, reputational concerns, and repeated harassment. This process of integration strengthened the explanatory depth of the study and supported a more nuanced understanding of online violence against women in Bangladesh.

3.5. Ethical considerations

Ethical considerations were observed throughout the research process. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and participants were informed about the purpose of the research before taking part. Informed consent was obtained prior to data collection, and respondents were free to decline participation or withdraw at any stage without consequence.

To protect participants' privacy, no personally identifying information was requested through the questionnaire. Responses were collected anonymously, and confidentiality was maintained throughout the handling and reporting of the data. Particular care was taken given the sensitive nature of online violence, and findings are presented in a manner that does not allow individual participants to be identified.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Demographic information

Table 2 presents the demographic characteristics of respondents who participated in the survey. The sample was predominantly composed of younger women, with 89% aged between 18 and 25 years. A smaller proportion of respondents were aged 26–35 years (9%), while 2% were aged 36–45 years. This indicates that the study largely reflects the experiences of younger digitally active women.

Table 2. Demographic characteristics of participants

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	18–25	89	89%
	26–35	9	9%
	36–45	2	2%
Location	Urban	75	75%
	Rural	25	25%
Educational Level	Tertiary	95	95%
	Secondary	4	4%
	No formal education	1	1%
Occupation	Student	89	89%
	Employed	11	11%
Internet Usage (Daily)	More than six hours	42	42%
	3–6 hours	33	33%
	1–3 hours	25	25%

In terms of location, most respondents were from urban areas (75%), whereas 25% were from rural areas. This distribution may reflect greater internet access and higher levels of digital engagement in urban settings.

Educational attainment was relatively high within the sample. The majority of respondents (95%) reported tertiary-level education, while 4% had secondary education and 1% reported no formal education. Regarding occupation, most respondents were students (89%), while 11% were employed.

Daily internet use was also relatively high. Around 42% of respondents reported spending more than six hours online each day, 33% reported using the internet for three to six hours daily, and 25% reported one to three hours of daily use. These figures suggest that the participants were regular and active internet users, which is relevant given the study's focus on online experiences.

4.2. Association between internet use and online abuse

A cross-tabulation analysis was initially conducted to explore how reported exposure to cyber violence varied among respondents with different levels of daily internet use. The preliminary patterns suggested a possible association between time spent online and experiences of online abuse.

Respondents who reported spending longer periods on the internet appeared somewhat more likely to report experiences of online violence than those with lower levels of daily use. In particular, participants who used the internet for more than six hours per day appeared to report relatively greater exposure to different forms of cyber abuse. These findings provided an initial indication that higher levels of online engagement may be associated with increased reported experiences of harassment. However, this pattern should be interpreted cautiously, as no causal relationship can be inferred from the present analysis. Greater internet use may increase visibility, frequency of interaction, and exposure to wider online environments in which abuse may occur. This interpretation is also broadly consistent with wider discussions in the literature, where greater digital engagement is sometimes linked with increased exposure to online harassment or threatening behaviour.

4.3. Who harasses women online? Forms and actors of digital gender-based violence

Figure 2 illustrates the relationship between the types of online violence reported by respondents and the identities of the alleged perpetrators. The findings suggest that online violence against women in Bangladesh may occur in multiple forms and may involve actors both within and outside respondents' existing social networks.

Figure 2. Types of online violence experienced by respondents and the reported perpetrators

Survey responses indicated that 87% of participants reported having experienced some form of online harassment, while 13% reported no such experience. Given the purposive nature of the sample, these figures should be interpreted as reflecting the experiences of the study participants rather than the wider population. Nevertheless, they suggest that online harassment was a common concern among the women who took part in this research.

Among the reported forms of abuse, online harassment, including name-calling, offensive comments, and abusive messages, appeared to be the most common experience. A large proportion of these incidents was attributed to strangers. However, respondents also identified friends and acquaintances as perpetrators, indicating that online abuse may not arise solely from anonymous actors but may also emerge from existing social relationships. This pattern is broadly consistent with literature identifying online harassment as one of the most common forms of technology-facilitated gender-based violence (Jane, 2017; Powell & Henry, 2019).

Another notable form of abuse reported by participants was impersonation, in which individuals allegedly created false profiles or accounts using the victim's identity. Figure 2 suggests that both strangers and known persons were associated with such incidents. This may indicate that perpetrators sometimes use personal information or images to create false identities, potentially causing reputational harm and compromising online safety. Similar concerns have been identified in previous research on cyber harassment (Henry & Powell, 2018).

Respondents also reported experiences relating to hate speech, stalking, sextortion, and doxing, demonstrating the multidimensional nature of technology-facilitated abuse. Reports of hate speech involved different categories of perpetrators, suggesting that women may encounter degrading or hostile language from multiple sources in online environments. Existing studies on digital misogyny have argued that such abuse may function as a means of intimidation or as an attempt to silence women's participation in online discourse (Jane, 2019; Mantilla, 2015).

Similarly, stalking and doxing illustrate how digital technologies may be used to monitor individuals, issue threats, or disclose personal information without consent. These behaviours may create fear, insecurity, and psychological distress. Although image-based abuse and sextortion appeared less frequently in respondents' accounts, they remain serious forms of digital violence because they may involve coercion, threats, or the non-consensual use of intimate material. Prior research has identified these forms of abuse as particularly harmful because of their emotional and reputational consequences (Henry et al., 2020).

Importantly, the findings suggest that perpetrators were not limited to faceless online actors. While strangers accounted for a substantial share of reported incidents, many cases also involved friends, acquaintances, or intimate partners. This may indicate that online violence can reflect existing social relationships and wider power dynamics, supporting arguments about the intersection between technology-facilitated abuse and broader patterns of gender inequality or relational control (Powell & Henry, 2019).

Taken together, the findings indicate that online violence against women in Bangladesh may take multiple interrelated forms and may be perpetrated by both unknown individuals and persons within victims' social networks. These results highlight the importance of policy and institutional responses that address not only anonymous cyber harassment, but also abuse involving known individuals.

4.4. From silence to justice: reporting barriers and outcomes of Cyber violence cases

4.4.1. Barriers to reporting online violence

The findings suggest that barriers to reporting online violence can be broadly understood in two categories: structural barriers and sociocultural barriers. Structural barriers include limited trust in how institutions respond to complaints, perceived delays or inaction by authorities, and difficulties in filing formal reports. Sociocultural barriers include concerns about stigma, victim blaming, and possible reputational damage, all of which may discourage some individuals from reporting incidents.

Survey responses indicated that fear of shame or victim blaming was one of the commonly mentioned reasons for not reporting online abuse. This may reflect wider social attitudes relating to gender norms, family reputation, and community expectations. Several respondents expressed concern that reporting abuse could lead to social stigma, criticism, or negative reactions from family members and others around them. This pattern is broadly consistent with previous research suggesting that some forms of gender-based violence in digital spaces remain underreported because of concerns about blame and social judgement (Jane, 2017; Powell & Henry, 2019).

Some respondents also mentioned fear of retaliation, indicating concern that making a formal complaint could result in further harassment or threats from perpetrators. In addition, a smaller but still notable proportion of participants reported being unaware of available reporting mechanisms. This may suggest gaps in public knowledge about support services, complaint procedures, or legal options for seeking redress.

Figure 3. Reasons cited by respondents for not reporting incidents of online violence

Taken together, these findings indicate that underreporting of online violence may be influenced by a combination of institutional, social, and informational factors rather than by personal choice alone. Such barriers may reduce the likelihood of victims seeking formal assistance or pursuing available remedies.

4.4.2. Outcomes of reported incidents

The survey also examined cases in which respondents had attempted to report incidents of online violence. As shown in Figure 4, the most commonly reported outcome was that no action was taken following the complaint. This may suggest limitations in the practical implementation of legal protections and institutional responses to online violence.

Figure 4. Outcomes of reported incidents of online violence among respondents

A smaller proportion of respondents indicated that the matter was resolved without any formal sanction. This may reflect the use of informal or community-based approaches to resolving disputes rather than formal legal proceedings against alleged perpetrators. In contrast, several respondents reported that they were still waiting for a response, which may indicate delays in complaint handling or investigative processes.

Only a small number of respondents reported that offenders had been formally punished. This may suggest that obtaining formal remedies can be challenging for some victims. Similar concerns have been noted in earlier studies, which indicate that institutional responses to cyber violence are sometimes viewed as insufficient, potentially reducing confidence in legal mechanisms and discouraging future reporting (Henry & Powell, 2018).

These findings suggest that although legal frameworks exist to address cybercrime, respondents perceived gaps in their practical implementation. This may contribute to a disconnect between formal legal provisions and victims' experiences of seeking justice or support.

4.5. Consequences of online violence

This section examines the reported effects of online violence on women who experienced harassment through digital platforms such as social media. The findings revealed that online violence has significant psychological, behavioural, and social impacts on the victim of cyber violence, as revealed by the data collected through in-depth interviews. Key Outcomes The ramifications of online violence, as revealed in the analysis, can be summarised as the following: the strain of mental health problems, the strain of reduced participation in the online world, the strain of behavioural adaptation to online interaction, and the strain of the breakdown of social trust. These ramifications of online violence will be examined through the lenses of the General Strain Theory (GST) by Agnew (1992), which indicates that experiences of negative events or noxious events can lead to strain that can impact the victim's behavioural adaptations to the events. The figure below indicates the proportion of the respondents' experiences.

In line with the General Strain Theory, cyberbullying can be perceived as an ongoing source of negative stimuli that creates psychological strain, such as anxiety, shame, and emotional stress. To cope with the stress caused by the negative experiences, people engage in coping behaviours that help minimise their future risk of harm. In this study, these behaviours can be observed through behavioural changes like decreased use of online platforms, self-censoring, and avoiding certain websites.

The findings of the research reveal that cyber violence has an impact on the victims' psychological health. In the study, it was revealed that 70 per cent of the victims reported that they have experienced negative impacts on their mental health, such as anxiety, emotional stress, humiliation, and loss of self-confidence resulting from cyber harassment. These findings are similar to the study that revealed that technology-based gender-based violence can result in significant emotional stress for the victims (Henry & Powell, 2018; Jane, 2017). In the context of general strain theory, cyber harassment can be considered an enduring negative stimulus that can result in emotional stress for the victims (Agnew, 1992). In addition to the emotional stress, the victims of cyber violence reported physical stress, including tiredness (10 per cent). These findings reveal that cyber violence can have more than emotional consequences for the victims.

And online violence has significant implications for the participation of women in the virtual as well as the physical world. The findings revealed that 80 per cent of the participants agreed that they have been participating less in online debates or the online world because of experiences of cyber harassment. The participants felt that they had been holding back on online platforms because of the fear of further harassment for giving an opinion in the online world. In other studies, online harassment has been identified as one of the factors that reduces the participation of women in the online world and also limits their freedom of expression in the online world (Mantilla, 2015; Jane, 2019). The reduction in participation can be understood as an adaptive coping strategy in the context of general strain theory, where individuals try to circumvent environments that recreate strain in their lives. For example, 20% of the participants agreed that their participation level has not been affected by online harassment, as they felt that they were strong enough to participate in the online world despite the harassment faced by them.

The findings also indicate changes in respondents' online behaviour following experiences of abuse. Nearly 40% reported censoring their behaviour online in an attempt to reduce the likelihood of further harassment. In addition, 30% stated that they had reduced their overall online activity, while 20% reported avoiding specific platforms that they considered unsafe. Only 10% indicated that their online behaviour had remained unchanged. These responses suggest that online violence may influence how women engage with digital spaces and may lead some users to limit their online presence.

A further consequence identified in the study was reduced trust in online communities and interactions. Around one quarter of respondents reported that they had become less trusting of others online following experiences of harassment. Some participants indicated that this created feelings of insecurity when communicating with unfamiliar users or forming new online relationships. In addition, 5% stated that they had withdrawn completely from certain online spaces.

Figure 5. Impact of Online violence on victims

Overall, the findings suggest that online violence may affect not only individual wellbeing but also broader patterns of behaviour, participation, and trust in digital environments. These consequences indicate that the impact of cyber violence can extend beyond immediate incidents and may shape women's longer-term engagement with online spaces.

4.6. Awareness, legal protection, and institutional responses to Cyber violence

Bangladesh has enacted several laws intended to address cybercrime and related forms of online abuse, including the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Act 2006, the Digital Security Act 2018, and the Cyber Security Act 2023. These legal instruments provide a formal basis for responding to issues such as online harassment, defamation, identity misuse, and other forms of technology-facilitated abuse. However, the effectiveness of these measures may depend not only on the existence of legal provisions, but also on the extent to which they are implemented, understood, and accessible to those seeking protection.

Perceptions that legal safeguards are insufficient may therefore arise from a range of factors, including limited public awareness of available remedies, procedural complexity, delays in complaint handling, and uncertainty regarding enforcement processes. In this sense, concerns about inadequate protection may reflect practical barriers in accessing justice rather than the complete absence of legal measures.

This section examines respondents' awareness of legal mechanisms relevant to cyber violence against women in Bangladesh, their perceptions of the adequacy of existing protections, and their views on how institutional responses could be strengthened. It also considers how knowledge of legal rights and confidence in enforcement may shape willingness to seek formal remedies. As noted in previous research, the effectiveness of laws addressing technology-facilitated abuse often depends not only on statutory provisions, but also on their practical application and public accessibility (Powell & Henry, 2019).

4.6.1. Knowledge of legal provisions related to Cyber violence against women

The findings suggest that respondents had a moderate level of awareness regarding legal protections relevant to cyber violence against women. Survey results indicated that 55% of participants were aware of existing legal provisions intended to address online harassment and cybercrime. This suggests that a notable proportion of internet users possess at least some knowledge of formal mechanisms that may be used to seek protection or redress.

At the same time, 45% of respondents reported that they were not aware of such legal protections. This indicates that substantial gaps in public awareness may remain. Limited knowledge of legal rights, complaint procedures, and available reporting mechanisms may reduce the likelihood that victims seek institutional support or pursue formal remedies after experiencing online abuse.

These findings suggest that the existence of legal measures alone may not be sufficient if members of the public are unaware of how such protections operate in practice. In this sense, legal effectiveness may depend not only on legislation itself, but also on public information, accessibility, and awareness-building initiatives. Similar concerns have been raised in wider discussions of cybercrime governance, where limited legal awareness may weaken the practical reach of existing protections.

From the perspective of General Strain Theory (Agnew, 1992), experiences such as online harassment may create emotional stress and uncertainty for victims. Where individuals are also unaware of available support systems or legal remedies, these pressures may be compounded, potentially increasing feelings of helplessness and reducing willingness to seek formal assistance.

4.6.2. Perception of existing legal protections as sufficient

Respondents' views on the effectiveness of existing legal protections indicate a number of concerns. Around 60% of participants stated that current legal provisions were inadequate for effectively addressing cyber violence against women. In contrast, 10% considered the existing protections to be effective, while 30% reported uncertainty regarding their effectiveness.

Figure 6. Awareness and legal provision

These responses may reflect a combination of factors, including limited public knowledge of legal processes, uncertainty about available remedies, and scepticism regarding institutional effectiveness. Although Bangladesh has introduced legal measures relating to cybercrime, respondents' perceptions suggest that

challenges may remain in relation to implementation, procedural delays, and practical accessibility. Similar concerns regarding the gap between formal legal provisions and their practical operation have been noted by Islam and Rahman (2023).

From the perspective of General Strain Theory (Agnew, 1992), institutional responses perceived as ineffective may add to the strain experienced by victims following online harassment. Where individuals believe that justice or support is unlikely to be achieved, they may experience greater frustration, uncertainty, or reluctance to seek formal remedies in the future.

4.6.3. Recommendations for enhancing safeguards against Cyber violence

Respondents were also asked to suggest ways in which protections against cyber violence could be improved. Half of the participants (50%) supported the introduction of stricter laws or stronger penalties as a means of deterring offenders and strengthening accountability.

A further 20% emphasised the importance of making reporting mechanisms more accessible, particularly through digital platforms and social media channels. This suggests that easier and more user-friendly reporting procedures may encourage victims to seek assistance more readily.

Another 15% highlighted the need for greater public awareness through educational initiatives focused on online safety, digital rights, and available legal protections. These responses indicate that awareness-building may be viewed as an important preventive measure alongside formal legal responses.

In addition, 10% of respondents recommended stronger support services for victims, including practical assistance, guidance, and responsive institutional mechanisms following incidents of abuse.

These responses suggest that participants viewed cyber violence as an issue requiring a multidimensional response. Rather than relying solely on legal sanctions, respondents pointed to the importance of combining effective laws, accessible reporting systems, public education, and victim support services. Such an integrated approach may help strengthen confidence in available protections and contribute to safer digital environments for women.

4.7. General discussion

The findings of this study offer a nuanced picture of online violence against women among the participants surveyed in Bangladesh and add to the emerging body of scholarship on technology-facilitated gender-based abuse in South Asia. Rather than appearing as a single or isolated phenomenon, online violence emerged as a layered experience shaped by interpersonal relations, social norms, patterns of digital engagement, and perceptions of institutional support. In this sense, the study suggests that online abuse is not merely a technological issue, but a social issue unfolding through technological spaces.

Within this sample, which was largely composed of younger (between the ages of 18 and 25 years) and digitally active women, experiences of online harassment were commonly reported. This is consistent with wider international literature indicating that younger women who maintain visible or active online presences may encounter heightened exposure to harassment, abuse, or unwanted attention in digital environments (Jane, 2017; Powell & Henry, 2019). However, the present findings should be understood in relation to the characteristics of the study group rather than as representative of all women internet users in Bangladesh.

One of the more significant insights of the study is that perpetrators were not perceived solely as anonymous strangers operating behind screens. While unknown individuals accounted for a substantial share of reported incidents, respondents also identified friends, acquaintances, and, in some cases, intimate partners. This finding suggests that online violence may at times mirror offline relationships, extending existing tensions, control, or hostility into digital spaces. The boundary between online and offline harm therefore appears less distinct than is sometimes assumed.

The study also highlights the personal consequences of online abuse. Respondents described experiences of anxiety, humiliation, emotional stress, and diminished confidence following incidents of harassment. For some, the impact did not end with the abusive message or threatening post; rather, it shaped subsequent behaviour. Many participants reported withdrawing from discussions, limiting their presence online, censoring their views, or avoiding particular platforms altogether. Digital participation, in these cases, became something to be managed cautiously rather than exercised freely. From the perspective of General Strain Theory, such responses may be understood as adaptive strategies developed in response to repeated stress or perceived risk (Agnew, 1992).

Another central theme concerns silence, or more precisely, the conditions that produce silence. Respondents frequently referred to limited confidence in institutional responses, concerns about social

judgement, and fear of victim blaming as reasons for not reporting incidents. Reporting online abuse therefore appeared not simply as an administrative decision, but as a socially situated act shaped by reputation, family expectations, and anticipated reactions from others. These findings indicate that formal legal remedies may remain underused where social costs are perceived to be high.

Perceptions of legal protection were similarly mixed. Although some respondents were aware of relevant laws in Bangladesh, including the Information and Communication Technology Act 2006, the Digital Security Act 2018, and the Cyber Security Act 2023, many expressed uncertainty about their effectiveness in practice. This suggests that the existence of legislation alone may not generate confidence unless accompanied by visible enforcement, accessible procedures, and responsive institutions. The distance between law on paper and law in experience remains an important issue in understanding victims' trust in formal systems.

Taken together, the findings suggest that online violence against women is best understood as a multidimensional issue situated at the intersection of gender relations, digital culture, and institutional capacity. It affects not only immediate wellbeing, but also confidence, participation, and trust within online environments. Addressing such violence may therefore require more than punitive legal responses alone. It may also call for public awareness, supportive reporting mechanisms, gender-sensitive institutional practices, and safer digital cultures that allow women to participate without fear of abuse.

5. CONCLUSION

This study examined online violence against women in Bangladesh through three interrelated aims: to explore the role of sociocultural factors in the occurrence of online violence against women, to assess the perceived adequacy of legal measures in addressing cyber violence against women, and to examine the occurrence and forms of online harassment experienced by women in digital spaces. In doing so, the study considered online violence through the combined lenses of prevalence, social context, and perceptions of legal protection among women who regularly use the internet.

With regard to the first aim, the findings suggest that sociocultural factors play an important role in shaping both experiences of abuse and responses to it. Respondents referred to concerns about stigma, victim blaming, reputational harm, and fear of negative reactions from family or community members. In addition, some incidents involved friends, acquaintances, or intimate partners rather than anonymous strangers alone. These findings indicate that online violence may, in some cases, reflect wider gender norms, existing social relationships, and offline power dynamics that continue within digital environments.

In relation to the second aim, respondents expressed mixed but generally cautious views regarding the adequacy of existing legal protections. Although Bangladesh has introduced legislation such as the ICT Act 2006, the Digital Security Act 2018, and the Cyber Security Act 2023, many participants questioned the practical effectiveness of these measures. Limited awareness of legal remedies, procedural complexity, delays in complaint handling, and uncertainty regarding enforcement were identified as possible barriers. This suggests that the existence of legal frameworks alone may not be sufficient unless accompanied by accessible procedures, effective implementation, and greater public confidence.

Concerning the third aim, the study found that participants reported a range of online abuses, including harassment, impersonation, hate speech, stalking, sextortion, and doxing. A particular strength of the study lies in the clear operationalisation of these forms of abuse, moving beyond the more generalised treatment often found in earlier literature. Survey responses suggested that online harassment was a common experience within this sample of digitally active women. The findings also indicate that greater online engagement may be associated with higher reported exposure to abuse, although this should be interpreted cautiously and not as evidence of causation.

The study further suggests that online violence does not occur solely through interactions with strangers on the internet. Abuse may also arise within friendships, acquaintanceships, and intimate relationships. This indicates that digital platforms can, at times, become extensions of offline social relations in which monitoring, intimidation, or controlling behaviour continues through online means.

Participants also described psychological and behavioural effects following experiences of cyber violence. Respondents reported anxiety, emotional distress, reduced confidence, and reluctance to participate in online activities. Many also described withdrawing from discussions, limiting their visibility, or practising self-censorship. Viewed through the lens of General Strain Theory, such responses may be understood as coping strategies intended to reduce further exposure to harm.

The research also identified a perceived gap between the existence of legislation and confidence in its practical effectiveness. Structural barriers included distrust in institutions, perceived inaction, and difficulties in accessing formal remedies. Cultural barriers included fear of stigmatisation, reputational damage, and victim blaming. Together, these factors may discourage reporting and reduce the practical effectiveness of available legal protections.

Nevertheless, the findings should be interpreted in light of the characteristics of the sample, which consisted largely of younger, educated, and digitally active women. The results should therefore not be assumed to represent the wider population of women in Bangladesh. Even so, the study offers useful insights for policymakers and practitioners. Educational institutions, for example, may play an important role in improving awareness of cybersecurity, digital rights, and available mechanisms for reporting online abuse.

The study also has several limitations. The sample size was relatively small, which limits the extent to which broader conclusions may be drawn. The use of purposive sampling may have introduced selection bias, while the online mode of data collection may have excluded individuals with limited internet access. In addition, the reliance on self-reported data may be affected by recall bias, underreporting, or selective disclosure, particularly given the sensitive nature of the topic. As the study was cross-sectional in design, it cannot determine changes over time or establish causal relationships.

Despite these limitations, the study offers timely insight into an issue of growing social importance in Bangladesh. Future research would benefit from larger and more diverse samples, longitudinal approaches, and comparative studies across regions or demographic groups. Further attention may also be given to emerging forms of abuse linked to artificial intelligence, deepfakes, and evolving platform technologies. Overall, the study highlights the importance of creating digital environments in which women are able to participate safely, confidently, and without fear of abuse.

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Notes

Disclosure of conflicts of interest

The authors declare that no perceived, potential, or actual conflict of interest exists.

Funding/Sponsorship

The authors confirm that no financial support was received and that the authors are not affiliated or associated with any organization or entity with a financial or non-financial interest in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

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